

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review Of The UV-Visible Spectroscopy's Method Development And Validation

Shraddha Khokrale*¹, Jeetu Lulla², Laxmikant Borse³

¹Student, Sandip Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Mahiravani, Nashik - 422213

²Lecturer, Sandip Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Mahiravani, Nashik - 422213

³Principal, Sandip Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Mahiravani, Nashik - 422213

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28 May 2024

Accepted: 01 June 2024

Published: 10 June 2024

Keywords:

Method development, validation, UV-visible spectroscopy, spectroscopy, analytical approach.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.11543658

ABSTRACT

The creation and verification of analytical methodologies are crucial to the production, development, and progression of pharmaceuticals. Pharmaceutical analysis significantly affects the quality assurance and control of both bulk drugs and pharmaceutical formulations. UV spectroscopy has been utilised in the pharmaceutical industry for the past three-and-a-half decades; it is an effective and significant analytical instrument. The processes that are required to determine the "identity, strength, quality, or purity" of these compounds are all part of the pharmaceutical analysis. The methodology for analysis involves the utilisation of colourless substances to measure how they absorb of light that is monochromatic in the near-ultraviolet (200–400 nm) range. In order to obtain the absorbance spectrum of a chemical in solution or solid form, UV-visible spectroscopy is utilised. The creation and verification of a spectroscopy using ultraviolet light method for the precise quantification of a substance are detailed in this study. The procedure was refined by means of distinct stages, and exhaustive evaluation validated its accuracy and dependability. The outcomes demonstrate its prospective utility in various domains for accurate substance quantification.

INTRODUCTION

The subfield of chemistry known as analytical chemistry is concerned with the identification of substances, samples, and mixtures' constituents quantitatively and qualitatively. There are two main kinds of analysis: qualitative and quantitative. The process of identifying analytes in

composites or samples is referred to as qualitative analysis. The determination of the amount of every element or analyse present in a mélange or sample is achieved via quantitative analysis. Pharmaceutical analysis is an integral component of the quality assurance and formulation procedures. It provides information regarding the

*Corresponding Author: Shraddha Khokrale

Address: Student, Sandip Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Mahiravani, Nashik - 422213

Email ✉: navnathkharat678@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

content, stability, identity, purity, and starting materials of the additives, active pharmaceutical constituents, and excipients. Additionally, it ensures the efficacy, safety, and quality of pharmaceuticals utilized in therapeutic environments. Pharmacological identity, purity, physical properties, and efficacy are the primary goals of analytical procedures. Methods are devised throughout the course of production, quality release, as well as long-term stability studies to aid in the testing of pharmaceuticals against specifications. A "regulatory analytical procedure" is utilized in the pharmaceutical industry to examine a distinguishing characteristic of active pharmaceutical constituents, pharmaceutical formulations, and unprocessed materials. Contemporary advanced analytical methods, including UV, HPLC, GLC, and HPTLC, are frequently utilized in routine or laboratory environments for the purposes of quantification or estimation.

Analytical Procedure: Analyte samples, whether quantitatively or qualitatively, or structurally, need the use of a predetermined methodology accompanied by detailed, procedural instructions. There are typically two main types of analytical procedures:

- I. Instrumental
- II. Non- Instrumental

I Instrumental Method:

A substance's composition can be ascertained by looking at its physical attributes. Conductometry, Potentiometry, and Electrogravimetry are a few examples.

Advantages:

- You may utilise small samples.
- Achieving high sensitivity is possible.
- Quickness of decision-making.
- Managing even the most intricate samples is a breeze.

II. Non-Instrumental Method:

These approaches include chemical processes. These approaches are based on volume and weight measurements. These procedures are sometimes referred to as the "classical analysis method".

Advantages:

- Approaches rely on precise measurements.
- In most cases, specialised training is unnecessary.
- The necessary gear is inexpensive.

Several approaches may be used for pharmaceutical analysis, and they are categorised in Figure no 1

Fig.1.Types of Method Analysis

Analytical chemistry can be broadly classified into two domains:

Quantitative:

It indicates the amount of active analytes that are present.

Qualitative:

It indicates the presence of active analytes.

Ultraviolet-

Examples of spectroscopic methods include visual, infrared, Raman, x-ray, nuclear magnetic, and atomic absorption and emission spectroscopy.

INTRODUCTION OF SPECTROSCOPY:

Spectroscopy refers to the scientific investigation of the interactions between matter and electromagnetic radiation. In these interactions, matter absorbs and emits energy in the form of radiation. Two distinct types of spectroscopy exist: absorption and emission. Absorption spectroscopy (UV-visible, infrared, nuclear magnetic resonance, microwave, and radio wave spectroscopy) examines the spectra of electromagnetic radiation that is absorbed by the sample. Flame photometry, fluorimetry, and emission spectroscopy are all methods of analysing electromagnetic radiation that a sample emits. A wide range of samples can be analysed using spectroscopy, which is also beneficial for the investigation of atomic and molecular structure. Atomic spectroscopy, encompassing flame photometry and atomic absorption spectroscopy, investigates the manner in which electromagnetic radiation induces energy fluctuations at the atomic level through its interaction with atoms. Molecular spectroscopy, including ultraviolet and infrared spectroscopy, is the scientific discipline concerned with the investigation of the ways in which electromagnetic radiation alters the energy of molecules through interaction.

UV-VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY:

By combining the visible and ultraviolet parts of the electromagnetic spectrum, UV-visible spectroscopy can determine the amount of light

absorbed at each wavelength. The visible and ultraviolet (UV, 200-400 nm) bands of electromagnetic energy are used in this absorption spectroscopy (400-800 nm-400 nm). The basic idea behind UV-Visible spectroscopy is that different spectra are produced when a sample or chemical component absorbs either visible or ultraviolet light. The process by which a molecule's electrons are stimulated as it absorbs ultraviolet light creates a reversal of the transition, which in turn produces ultraviolet emission spectrum. when a consequence, the amount of electronic energy inside the molecule goes from lower to greater when electrons migrate from one state to another. When using ultraviolet spectroscopy, the most common solvents utilised are water, methanol, ethanol, chloroform, cyclohexane, and dichloromethane. Purity, geometrical isomers, conjugation, and functional group detection are all accomplished via the use of ultraviolet spectroscopy. The concentration of solutes in a solution may be determined using spectrophotometer methods by analysing the quantity of light absorbed by a solution in a cuvette. The two-faced character of light is used in spectroscopy.

- Wave nature, which creates the visible spectrum of light
- Particle nature, which produces the photoelectric effect

These drugs are frequently analysed using a variety of analytical methods. Spectroscopy is one of the most used analytical methods for drug analysis. It is essentially the measurement of sunlight absorption by chemical compounds at certain, restricted wavelengths that mimic monochromatic light.

THEORY OF SPECTROPHOTOMETRY:

The three main ways in which light interacts with solutions and homogeneous media are reflection, absorption, and transmission.

Thus if,

I_0 is the intensity of radiation falling on the media.

I_r is the amount of radiations reflected

I_a is the amount of radiation absorbed &

I_t is the amount of radiation transmitted

Then,

$$I_0 = I_r + I_a + I_t,$$

I_r is negligible as compared to I_a & I_t ,

$$I_0 = I_a + I_t$$

Laws involved,

1. Beer's law

2. Lambert's law

1. Beer's Law:

The rate at which the intensity of radiation decreases with an increase in the concentration (c) of absorbing species in a homogeneous absorbing material passing through a monochromatic light beam is directly proportional to the intensity (I) of the incident light (radiation).

2. Lambert's law:

The rate at which the intensity of radiation decreases with the thickness of the absorbing media when a monochromatic light beam passes through it is exactly proportional to the intensity of the input light (radiation).

Beer's –Lambert's Law:

"Light emission may be lessened when it passes through a simple cell with an arrangement of absorbing substances; the rate of intensity reduction is proportional to the medium's thickness and the concentration of absorbing substances."

Mathematically Beer-Lamberts law is expressed as:

Where,

$$A = abc$$

A = absorbance or optical density

a = absorptivity or extinction coefficient

TERMS USED IN UV/VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY:

A. Chromophore:

1. Chromophores are the parts of molecules that give a molecule its color.
2. Functional groups with numerous bonds that may absorb radiations above 200 nm caused by transitions between $n \rightarrow$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$. For example, NO_2 , $\text{N}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}=\text{N}$, $\text{C}=\text{C}$, $\text{C}=\text{S}$, and so on.

To evaluate the UV-visible spectrum, the following aspects should be considered:

1. UV spectrophotometers cannot detect non-conjugated alkenes because of their significant absorption below 200 nm.
2. There is a faint absorption band between 200 and 300 nm for compounds with non-conjugated carbonyl groups.

B. Auxochrome:

- i. Those functional groups that are bound to chromophores and change their capacity to absorb light by changing the wavelength or intensity of that light.
- ii. The non-bonding electron functional group that, when coupled to a chromophore, changes the absorption wavelength and intensity but is ineffective in the near ultraviolet (UV) spectrum.
- iii. Take benzene, phenol, and aniline as examples; their λ_{max} values are (255 nm), (270 nm), and (280 nm), respectively.

INSTRUMENTATION OF UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETRY:

1. Light Source
2. Filters and Monochromators
3. Sample cell
4. Detectors
5. Recording Devices

Fig.2. Instrumentation of Uv-Visible Spectroscopy

1. Light Source:

Characteristics of a Light Source:

1. It should not fluctuate and should be steady.
2. Enough light should be produced by it.
3. It must be cost-effective.
4. It ought to continuously emit a spectrum.
5. Its design and operation should be straightforward.

Types of Radiation Source:

1. Hydrogen lamp:

These reliable, steady lamps continuously produce radiation ranging from 160 to 380 nm. It is composed of high-pressure hydrogen gas, which produces an electrical discharge. Radiation is created by energised hydrogen molecules.

2. Deuterium lamp:

A deuterium lamp is a gas discharge lamp that is widely used as a UV source. It radiates between 160 and 450 nanometers.

3. Tungsten lamp:

Tungsten lamps are the most prevalent kind of light source used in spectrophotometers. It is utilised for the visible spectrum and has a wavelength range of around 330 to 900 nm. It's constructed from a tungsten filament wrapped in a glass envelope.

4. Xenon discharge lamp:

A discharge light source containing xenon gas within the bulb is known as a xenon lamp. Xenon radiation has a wavelength of 250 to 600 nm.

2. Monochromator:

This device isolates the needed wavelength's radiation from the continuous spectrum's wavelength. Monochromators typically consist of slits and prisms. The vast majority of spectrophotometers are double beam. Prisms that spin are utilised to help distribute the radiation from the primary source. Choosing the different light wavelengths that the prism will separate. In order to capture the light from the source, the prism separates its different wavelengths as it spins, allowing a succession of steadily increasing wavelengths to flow through the slits. A second prism may be used to further split the monochromatic beam that was picked by the slit into two beams.

3. Sample and reference cells:

- The sample container should be UV-visible radiation-transparent.
- The reference solution is transmitted via the second split beam, while the sample solution passes through the first.
- Cells store both the reference solution and the sample.
- The cells are made of quartz or silica.
- Glass absorbs UV rays, making it unsuitable for use with cells.

4. Detector:

Two photocells are the standard components of a UV spectroscopy detector.

One photocell in the reference cell and one detector in the sample cell take in the light. In comparison to the sample cell, the reference cell's radiation beam is much stronger. Therefore, pulsing or alternating currents are produced by the photocells.

Types of Detectors:

1. Barrier layer cell / Photovoltaic cell
2. Phototube / Photo emissive tube
3. Photomultiplier tube

5. Amplifier:

The photocells' alternating current is received by an amplifier. An amplifier is connected to a miniature servomotor. Given the typically low current generated by photocells, the principal function of the amplifier is to multiplex the signals so as to generate distinct and recordable signals.

6. Recording devices:

A pen recorder, which is frequently linked to a computer, is frequently connected to the amplifier. The computer generates the spectrum of the specified compound and stores all generated data.

DIFFERENT UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC MULTICOMPONENT ANALYSIS METHODS:

There are some methods:

1. Simultaneous equation method:

Given specific conditions, the simultaneous equation approach (Vierordt's method) may be used to identify both drugs (x and y) in a sample containing two absorbing medications that both absorb at the other's λ max.

The necessary data is:

- a_{x1} and a_{x2} are the absorptivities of x at λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively.
- The corresponding absorptivities of y at λ_1 and λ_2 , or a_{y1} and a_{y2} .

2. Difference Spectrophotometry:

The distinction the utilisation of spectrophotometry techniques has the potential to substantially enhance the accuracy and selectivity of analyses conducted on substances that

incorporate absorbing interferences. The basic elements of this approach are as follows: The value being measured is the absorbance difference between two equimolar solutions of the analytes (chemical compounds with distinct spectral characteristics).

3. Derivative Spectrophotometry:

Differential spectrum analysis (DS) utilises differentiation to convert a fundamental, zero-order spectrum of a normal spectrum into spectra of its first, second, or higher derivatives. Differentiating the zero-order spectrum may result in the following: separation of overlapping signals; enhancement of mixture resolution through improved detection of minute spectral features; elimination of background induced by the presence of other compounds in the sample; and augmentation of sensitivity and specificity.

4. Derivative ratio spectra methods:

For the purpose of resolving binary mixtures, the generation of ratio spectra forms the basis of this simple spectrophotometric method developed by Salinas et al. This technique enables the identification of active chemicals even in the presence of potentially interfering compounds and excipients, by permitting the utilisation of the wavelength at which analytical signals exhibit their maximum and minimum values on multiple occasions.

5. Double divisor ratio spectra derivative method:

The technique relies on measurements made at either the maximum or lowest wavelengths, as well as the derivative of the ratio spectrum. By dividing the absorption spectra of the ternary mixture by the reference spectrum of a mixture comprising only two of the three compounds in the combination, one can derive the derivative of the ratio spectrum. It is exclusively relevant to mixtures in which the concentration ratio of the two substances interfering (which function as a double divisor) is established. In contrast, the ratio

of two interfering component concentrations should be identical for the calibration, prediction, and unknown samples.

METHODOLOGY: UV –VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY:

METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

A steady stream of novel pharmaceuticals are introduced to the market on a daily basis. Occasionally, the period from the time a drug is introduced to the market until it is included in pharmacopoeias can be quite lengthy. This occurs as a result of the potential hazards associated with the continued and increased use of these drugs, the introduction of more effective drugs in response to competition, the emergence of new toxicity reports, and the increase in patient resistance. In some instances, pharmacopoeias might not include standard scientific procedures for these medications. Consequently, it is critical to establish a novel explanatory framework for these medications. In order to assess the defined normal for a pharmaceutical compound or dosage form, an authorised analytical method is utilised. A candidate proposes employing the option logical method as opposed to the administrative systematic approach. Moreover, due to the potential impact of medications on human life, quality control is an absolute necessity for all services and products. A critical component of the development process for novel pharmaceutical products is security testing. Soundness testing aims to furnish substantiation regarding the temporal evolution of the characteristics of a constituent or component of a pharmaceutical product, as it is exposed to diverse environmental influences, including temperature, moisture, and light. The utilisation of this evidence permits the formulation of capacity conditions, retest intervals, and practical usability timeframes. The pragmatic timetable for determining the efficacy of medication items is significantly influenced by two primary components: the dynamic medication

test and the degradants produced during the soundness investigation. In order to determine which wavelength or wavelengths yield optimal results for a specific analysis on a given instrument, it is necessary to devise a method that accounts for the errors that the instrument may introduce. Several factors come into play when determining which option is superior: ruggedness, range, selectivity, linearity, accuracy, precision, and sensitivity. Prior to beginning any analysis, the optimisation parameter or parameters must be selected and the requirements must be established; it is not feasible to optimise all of these parameters simultaneously.

Method creation is completed:

1. Regarding novel goods
2. Regarding current goods

To sum up, the motivations for the creation of more modern drug analysis methodologies include:

- It is possible that neither the drug nor the drug combination is officially recognised in any pharmacopoeia.
- A suitable expository approach for treatment could not be accessible in writing due to patent laws.
- The utilisation of analytical systems as pharmaceutical excipients may not invariably be practical.
- Analytical techniques for drugs that have been merged with other drugs may be unattainable.
- Choosing an accurate assay methodology to determine a formulation's composition is an essential step in developing an analytical approach. Asserting the suitability of an analytical technique for laboratory use is referred to as analytical method development. The preparation of analytical techniques must adhere to the acceptance criteria and procedures specified in ICH guidelines Q2 (R1). They are required for use in GMP and GLP environments.

Here are the prerequisites for developing methods:

The following criteria need to be satisfied in order to build a method:

- Competent analysts
- Calibrated and certified instruments
- Methods with documentation
- Dependable benchmarks
- Selection and integrity of the sample

METHOD VALIDATION:

The term "method validation" refers to the steps taken to ensure that an analytical technique is appropriate for a particular test. Method validation results, which are a vital element of any reliable analytical procedure, can be utilised to evaluate the quality, consistency, and dependability of analytical outcomes. Validation is performed to guarantee that measurements produced by a measurement procedure are accurate. One can evaluate the dependability, consistency, and quality of analytical data by examining the results obtained from method validation. It is a critical component of any reliable analytical process. Method validation, which is defined as the "The process of creating recorded proof, known as "validation," ensures a high degree of confidence that the equipment or product being evaluated will meet the criteria of the planned analytical applications.

The significance of validation

1. Quality assurance.
2. Time-sensitive
3. Streamlining procedures
4. A decrease in waste of high grade
5. Higher productivity
6. Refusing to make capital purchases
7. A decrease in complaints regarding process-related errors.

ANALYTICAL METHOD VALIDATION:

Analytical methodologies are absolutely essential for the development of new medications, formulation and preformulation research, stability

studies, and quality control inspections. This strategy must be uncomplicated, precise, accurate, cost-effective, and user-friendly. It is necessary to conduct approach validation both during development and in use. Analytical validation refers to the process of assessing and substantiating that an analytical method successfully accomplishes its designated objectives.

ELEMENTS OF VALIDATION:

1. Design Qualification (DQ):

In this certification, GMP conformance for the design should be demonstrated. The apparatus design principles ought to ensure that the objectives of the GMP are fulfilled. It is essential to review the mechanical drawings and design elements provided by the equipment manufacturer.

2. Installation Qualification (IQ):

Installation qualification is an essential process that must be undertaken on newly constructed or modified equipment, systems, and structures. The certification for installation should encompass the subsequent critical domains. Conducting an examination of the installations of instrumentation, infrastructure, services, and equipment while collecting the provider's operational guidelines, maintenance specifications, and calibration requirements. Verification of construction materials, maintenance sources, and spare parts.

3. Operational Qualification (OQ):

This stage ought to follow IQ and encompass the subsequent: assessments developed on the basis of knowledge of the processes, systems, and instruments that establish minimum and maximum operational thresholds. An occasional usage of the term "worst case conditions" is to describe that.

4. Performance Qualification (PQ):

Following the conclusion of IQ and OQ, the subsequent qualification that must be accomplished is PQ. The PQ should comprise the subsequent: Investigations involving prototypes,

substitutes, or modelled products. Developing knowledge of the facilities, systems, apparatus, and processes can yield these outcomes. Include tests that possess upper and lower bound criteria.

TYPES OF VALIDATION:

- Prospective process validation
- Retrospective process validation
- Concurrent validation

1. Prospective Validation:

Implementing written evidence to support the claims or capabilities of a system in accordance with a predetermined strategy. This authentication is performed prior to the releasing of new products.

2. Retrospective Validation:

It is the generation of written evidence that substantiates the claim or performance of a system, derived from an examination and evaluation of the accessible data. This is achieved by utilising manufacturing, testing, and control data collected on a previously released product.

3. Concurrent Validation:

It is the process of utilising data generated during system construction to generate written substantiation of what a system does or purports to do.

PARAMETERS (COMPONENTS) OF METHOD:

1. Accuracy
2. Precision
3. Linearity
4. Limit of detection
5. Limit of quantitation
6. Specificity
7. Range
8. Robustness

1. Accuracy:

An essential validation metric employed to assess the overall accuracy of a model's predictions is accuracy. It is computed using the proportion of precisely predicted instances to the total number of instances. While accuracy provides a

comprehensive evaluation of a model's performance, asymmetrical datasets consisting primarily of a single class may not be optimal for assessing accuracy. In order to provide a more comprehensive evaluation under such conditions, additional metrics such as accuracy, recall, and F1 score are often incorporated.

2. Precision:

Precision quantifies the veracity of a model's positive predictions. The ratio of correct guesses to the total number of correct and incorrect predictions is used to determine it. Particularly useful in scenarios where minimising false positives is critical, precision emphasises the accuracy of positive predictions for every occurrence predicted as positive by the model.

3. Linearity:

Linearity refers to the characteristic of a mathematical connection or system in which the output is precisely proportional to the input. Visualising the relationship between variables in linear systems, where doubling the input results in a doubling of the output, is possible with a straight line. Linearity, a fundamental concept in mathematics, is crucial to numerous fields, including engineering, physics, and statistics. Non-linear interactions deviate from this proportionality by manifesting unique behaviours in response to changes in input and output.

4. Limit of detection:

An analytical method's Limit of Detection (LOD) is the lowest concentration or amount of a chemical that can be recognised reliably but not necessarily measured. It is the moment when the signal generated by the method is slightly elevated above the baseline or background noise, thereby enabling the detection of the substance. LOD is an indispensable metric in analytical chemistry and other scientific fields; it indicates the capacity of a measurement method to detect minuscule amounts of a substance in a sample and its sensitivity.

5. Limit of quantitation:

(LOQ) refers to the minimum concentration of a substance that can be detected and quantified with precision using a particular analytical method. The sensitivity metric is a measure of the lowest concentration of the analyte in a sample that can be detected with a high level of precision and accuracy. As LOQ requires a relatively precise measurement of the substance's quantity in addition to determining its presence, it is typically greater than the Limit of Detection. The reliability of quantitative data in analytical chemistry and other scientific fields is contingent upon this parameter.

6. Specificity:

The capacity of a measurement or diagnostic test to precisely detect and differentiate a certain target or analyte without reacting negatively with other substances known as specificity. High specificity refers to the ability of a method to accurately identify the target analyte in assays or tests without causing false positives as a result of interference from unrelated chemicals. In several disciplines, including biology, chemistry, and medicine, specificity is essential for ensuring that the outcomes accurately reflect the presence or absence of the targeted target.

7. Range:

"Range" frequently refers to the permissible range of values for a parameter or variable when it comes to validation parameters. Verifying that a given value is inside a predetermined range of acceptable values is known as range validation. This provides a means to recognize and manage values that are beyond the expected bounds, assisting in ensuring that the input or output of a system, process, or model is within a given range. In many domains, including as software development, data validation, and experimental measurements, range validation is frequently employed.

8. Robustness:

The term "robustness" describes a system or process's capacity to continue operating normally

and exhibiting stability in the face of uncertainty or shocks. A robust system can withstand or adjust to mistakes, alterations, or unanticipated inputs without suffering a major loss in overall performance. Robustness may be used in a variety of situations, including statistical models, control systems, software, algorithms, and other areas where resilience to change and dependability are crucial. The objective is to develop systems that can function well in a variety of demanding conditions while reducing the influence of unanticipated circumstances.

CONCLUSION:

UV-visible spectroscopy stands out as a fundamental and indispensable tool in pharmaceutical analysis and material science. Its reliability, affordability, and simplicity make it a preferred method for estimating the concentration of absorbing species accurately. Moreover, UV-Vis spectroscopy plays a crucial role in analyzing the optical characteristics of polymer nanocomposites, shedding light on the relationship between matrices and nanofillers, thereby enhancing the properties of these materials for various technological applications. By providing a quantitative measure of light absorption, UV-Vis spectroscopy enables researchers to determine the identity, strength, quality, and purity of compounds, essential aspects in pharmaceutical development and manufacturing. Overall, with its firm theoretical basis and reproducibility, UV-visible spectroscopy continues to be a cornerstone technique in analytical chemistry, facilitating advancements in both pharmaceuticals and materials science.

REFERENCES:

1. Kenkel J. Analytical Chemistry for Technicians. Lewis Publishers. 2003.
2. Kissinger PT. Instant Notes: Analytical Chemistry. Clin Chem. 2002; 48(12): 2303.
3. Harvey D. Modern analytical chemistry. McGraw-Hill. 2000.

4. Ravisankar P, Navya CN, Pravallika D, Sri DN. A review on step- by-step analytical methodvalidation. IOSR J Pharm. 2015; 5(10): 7-19.
5. Jeffery GH. Textbook of quantitative chemical analysis. Longman. 1989.
6. Chatwal GR, Anand SK. Instrumental Methods of Chemical Analysis. Himalaya Publishing House. 2002
7. Susmeena Tabassum Kapatrala, Vinod Kumar Kondreddy, Swapna Kandlapalli, Tejaswi Male. Method Development and Validation for the Estimation of Etizolam and Propranolol Hydrochloride in bulk and Combined Dosage Forms by Simultaneous and Derivative Spectroscopic Methods. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis. 2021; 11(4): 263-269.
8. Sushil D. Patil, Sayali K. Chaure, Sanjay Kshirsagar. Development and validation of UV spectrophotometric method for Simultaneous estimation of Empagliflozin and Metformin hydrochloride in bulk drugs. Asian J. Pharm. Ana. 2017; 7(2): 117-123.
9. Agrawal O.D, Telang N.B. Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of Benfotiamine in Bulk and Dosage Form. Asian J. Pharm. Ana. 2016; 6(3): 133-137.
10. Santosh Gada, Anand Kumar Y, Saritha, C. Mallikarjuna Setty. UV Spectrophotometric Development and Validation of Zidovudine API and in Marketed Zidovudine Tablet Dosage form. Asian journal of pharmaceutical analysis 2018; 8(4): 195-202.
11. K. Pramod, Shahid H. Ansari, Javed Ali. UV Spectrophotometric Method for the Quantification of Eugenol during in Vitro Release Studies. Asian J. Pharm. Ana. 2013; 3(3): 86-89.
12. Mansi J. Chaudhari, Suraj R. Chaudhari, Shailesh S. Chalikwar, Atul A. Shirkhedkar. Application of Area Under Curve Technique for UV- Spectrophotometric Determination of Luliconazole in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Formulation. Asian J. Pharm. Ana. 2018; 8(1): 45-48.
13. Sama Venkatesh, Sirimalla Jyothi, Rajeswari Chiluka, Yenumula Padmavathi. Development of UV- Spectrophotometric Method for the Simultaneous Estimation of Nateglinide and Piperine in Combined Tablet dosage form. Asian J. Pharm. Ana. 2020; 10(3): 134-140.
14. G. Krishnamoorthy, C. Diana Priyadarshini, R. Senthamarai. Spectrophotometric method of Choline Bitartrate in bulk and its tablet formulation. Asian J. Pharm. Ana. 2012; 2(4): 114-115.
15. Mahawar Sheetal. A Simple Ultraviolet Spectrophotometric Method for the Estimation of Docetaxel in Bulk Drug and Formulation. Asian J. Pharm. Ana. 2013; 3(2): 48-52.
16. Shaik Bima Benazir, Jorige Archana, Mogili Sumakanth. Method Development and Validation of Empagliflozin in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form using UV Spectroscopy. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis. 2021; 11(2): 123
17. Pavan Chavan, Sandip Bandgar, Santosh Gejage, Sagar Patil, Shitalkumar Patil. Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of Itraconazole in Bulk Drug and Solid Dosage Form. Asian J. Pharm. Res. 2021; 11(1): 13-16.
18. Audumbar Mali, Santosh Jadhav, Rahul Gorad, Aamer Qazi, Ritesh Bath, Manojkumar Patil, Ashpak Tamboli. Simultaneous UV Spectrophotometric Methods for Estimation of Cefixime Trihydrate and Ofloxacin in Bulk and Tablet

- Dosage Form. *Asian J. Pharm. Res.* 2016; 6(2): 100-106
19. Kumar S. Spectroscopy of organic compounds. *Cosmic rays.* 2006; 10: 4.
20. Luxminarayan L, Sharma N, Viswas A, Khinchi MP. A review on chromatography techniques. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development.* 2017; 1-8.
21. Chauhan A, Mittu B, Chauhan P. Analytical method development and validation: a concise review. *J Anal Bioanal Tech.* 2015; 6(1): 1-5.
22. Ravisankar P, Gowthami S, Rao GD. A review on analytical method development. *Indian J Res Pharm Biotech.* 2014; 2(3): 1183.
23. Lavanya G, Sunil M, Eswarudu MM, Eswaraiah MC, Harisudha K, Spandana BN. Analytical method validation: An updated review. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2013; 4(4): 1280
24. Nandha Kumar L. An overview of pharmaceutical Validation- Quality Assurance view point. *International journal of Research in pharmacy and Chemistry* 2011; 1(4): 1003-1014
25. Sharma Tejal. Process validation: An Essential in the Pharmaceutical Industry. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development* 2011; 3(10): 133-142.
26. Berry, I.R. and Nash, R.A. *Pharmaceutical Process Validation*, 2nd edition, 1993 (Marcel Dekker).
27. Juran, J. *Quality Control Handbook* 3rd edition, 1974 (McGraw-Hill).
28. Jones, P. Harmonization of international GMPs. *Pharmaceutical Engng*, 1999, 19(1), 60–64.
29. Nash R.A., Alfred H.W., *Pharmaceutical Process Validation*, 3rd ed., Marcel Dekker, New York, 2003, 159-180.
29. Lambert J., *Validation Guidelines for Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms.* Healyh Canada/ Health Products and Food Branch Inspectorate, 2004: 7-15.
30. Nikam Umed A, Jadhav Abhijit V, Salunkhe V. R, Magdum C. S. An Overview of Pharmaceutical Process Validation of Solid Dosage Form Current Pharma Research., 2013; 3(2): 824-835.
31. Sharma T, Solanki NS, Mahatma OP. Process validation an essentially in the Pharmaceutical Industry. *Int J Pharm Res & Development.* 2011; 3(10): 133-142.
32. Goldberg, E. *Handbook of Downstream Processing*, 1997(Blackie Academic and Professional).
33. The office of the Federal Register, National Archives and Records Administration, 1999.
34. *Guideline on General Principles of Process Validation*, 1987(Center for Drugs and Biologics, Food and Drug Administration).

HOW TO CITE: Shraddha Khokrale, Jeetu Lulla, Laxmikant Borse, A Review Of The UV-Visible Spectroscopy's Method Development And Validation, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 6, 527-538. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11543658>